

Is It The Society Or The Family That Digitalizes The Child?

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Abstract

² The COVID-19 epidemic has markedly accelerated the use of digital technologies in the shift towards a digital education system. The first segment of the research investigated the influence of digital media on our lives. The second segment of the pertinent research elucidated the impacts of alterations in family function and structure, lifestyle, and modernization in the post-digital era on children. The final segment of the research assessed the impact of digitalization on society by contrasting traditional childhood culture with contemporary childhood culture. The last section of the pertinent research examined the impact of digitalization, particularly concerning children, on child development.

Research indicates that when a newborn initially perceives the world, the family significantly influences the development of the child's personality characteristics. The parent-child connection significantly influences the development of these features (maternal involvement in professional life, heightened consumerism, and extensive urbanization).

Keywords: *Digital Parenting, Digital Childhood, Social Change*

²This study was written based on Sümeyra RAHMANOĞLU's article titled "IS IT SOCIETY OR FAMILY THAT DIGITALIZES CHILDREN?" which she wrote under the supervision of Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kürşat ŞAHİN YILDIRIMER at the Northwest University Graduate School of Education .

1.INTRODUCTION

The connection of children with digital media is rising in Turkey and globally, becoming a significant concern for educators, parents, and academics. This tendency has intensified, particularly during the epidemic, as youngsters have been more exposed to digital media. The working schedules of parents, the proliferation of digital education platforms, and other factors have augmented the duration youngsters spend in front of screens. Merdin, 2023, p. 8093. Previously, the perceived dangers for children originated from the external environment rather than the domestic sphere; however, contemporary threats arise from excessive engagement with smartphones, tablets, and computer screens. Children are maturing in an environment where touch screens are often concealed beneath their pillows, which is believed to stem from their attempts to navigate their living conditions.

Swift advancements in technology and communication have made digital media central to our existence. Digital media refers to information accessed via internet-based platforms, cellphones, tablets, computers, and other electronic devices. (Merdin, 2023, p.8093). Digitalization has made communication technologies readily accessible, with parents seeing home screens as trustworthy. The erosion of childhood culture and the integration of technology into daily life have progressed towards digitalization, presenting contemporary challenges.

Utilization of social media platforms is among the most prevalent activities of contemporary youth. Any website that facilitates social interaction may be classified as a social media platform (Ulusoy and Bostanci, 2014). Children navigate their connection with media via several platforms, including television, the internet, smartphones, tablets, smart boards, social media, computer use, and video games. The bond the youngster forms with social media is as significant as the communication established with persons in their immediate surroundings. As the child is unable to independently comprehend his/her existence while exploring the environment, the behaviors of those with whom he/she frequently interacts during development are driven by the pursuit of innovation, the desire for societal approval, and the need to remain relevant within the community. The child's adaptation to technology circumstances, inability to embody characters created in games, departure from conventional gaming culture, and assumption of roles within digital game culture underscores the need of their regulation by digital media. Media technologies significantly influence children's socialization, learning, and development in an environmental context. Environmental elements influencing game narratives, consumption habits, hydration, character representations, and fashion choices are mostly governed by contemporary media. Media instruments may influence behavior, cognition, and emotions by the messages they transmit

(Durmuş, 2021, p.138). Currently, the influence of media alters children's social communication styles, diminishes face-to-face interactions, amplifies a visual-centric popular culture, and fosters a generation that utilizes and consumes information rather than engaging in critical thinking and inquiry. The competitive generation's dissatisfaction with purchased products and desire for superior models underscores their subjugation to digital media influence.

In this context, the "Y Generation," born between 1980 and 2000 and known as the "Millennial Generation," has transformed modern cultural paradigms through digitalization amid rapid temporal shifts. The "Z Generation," born from 2000 to 2012, has encountered remnants of the virtual realm, while the "Alpha Generation," born in 2013, has emerged as individuals who engage predominantly with contemporary technological devices rather than traditional games. The second revolution has proven to be at least as impactful as the revolution initiated by the advent of mass communication technologies almost a century ago, transforming our era into a digital age and society into a digital society (Biricik, 2022, p.110).

Historically, physical games were often played in public spaces, however contemporary preferences lean towards digital games enjoyed in domestic and virtual settings. The portability of digital games facilitates access under many conditions, contributing to the phenomenon of gaming addiction among youngsters.

In the pre-digital era of childhood, children engaged with one another in their neighborhoods, participated in games with peers, communicated, and so practiced the skills of maturity from an early age. Children globally engaged in almost identical activities (such as rope skipping, hopscotch, and hide-and-seek), so imparting a universal characteristic to children's games. These universal games facilitated the development of children's social skills. Games facilitated children's acquisition of communication skills, cooperation, and adherence to established norms. (Biricik, 2022, p. 111)

With digitization, we must adapt to the evolving era, and we see changes in the character of games. The digital revolution has unveiled the transformational characteristics of our current era, with the

technology that have facilitated this revolution reshaping production, reproduction, consumption, socialization, and cultural phenomena (Biricik, 2022, p.110). The distinction of children's game styles for assessing their leisure activities; consumption of games and toys, the alteration in the quality of toy materials; reproduction, the evolution of contemporary circumstances into a nuclear family framework; has influenced the socialization process and compelled children to mature in isolation. The revolution instigated by mass media has progressively eradicated neighborhood games passed down through generations, resulting in a transition to a digital society. Digitalization significantly influences the transformation of social structures, as contemporary children exhibit a preference for digital games that do not foster social interactions or cooperative relationships. Traditional neighborhood games and cultural pastimes, such as "my hand is on you," "open the door," "beyblade," "five stones," and "dodgeball," have become unfamiliar. Children are increasingly detached from the concept of time management, often spending extensive periods in front of digital screens. The nature of play has evolved, with materials no longer derived from natural sources—such as stones, soil, wood, and branches. Consequently, the quality of play diminishes, and consumption becomes obligatory, as children gravitate towards plastic toys that pose health risks, favoring ready-made options that stifle their creativity. The function and form of the family, the fundamental social unit responsible for the transmission of both financial and spiritual riches between generations, evolves along with societal development. Aslan (2002, p. 26).

This transformation is believed to have introduced new notions of motherhood in contemporary society. One of these conceptions is "Blogger Motherhood." The bloggers, referred to as "Instagram Moms/Instamoms," have garnered significant attention on social media and have emerged as a prominent venue for mothers to engage with one another. Özkan and Özer (2022). This circumstance has transformed social life and significantly influences children's lives by forming individuals.

The personalities of persons that begin to develop in infancy are influenced by their parents' attitudes and inherent traits (Yıldırım 2023, p.79). Currently, due to the convergence of media, mothers disseminate ultrasound images on social platforms prior to childbirth, curate "outdoor photographs" designed to garner likes in the digital realm, and organize "gender reveal party kits" before ascertaining the child's sex (female or male), while employing the notion of "Mom" within the gender reveal party framework. Adorning a crystal crown embellished with stone embroidery, with words such as "to be," "Best Mom," and "Baby Shower," which is arranged for enjoyment immediately before to the delivery. The family is believed to engage in "Digital Parenting" roles introduced by contemporary life, including concepts such as "shower parties," decorating the

hospital room prior to the mother's labor, displaying statements like "It's a boy" or "Princess is coming" on the wall, and arranging for a "Birth Photographer" to capture images of the child at the moment of birth. This circumstance underscores the need for parents and society to address the impacts of digitalization on children.

2. METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

2.1. Purpose of the Research

Numerous internal and external elements influence the digitization of children in contemporary society. The primary influence of external forces is seen to be the media in the digital transformation process. Children are now influenced more by digital media culture than by local culture. As a family and community, they endeavor to construct the essence of enjoyment in their lives while negating their existence in front of the digital screen. The evolving cultural system has facilitated the proliferation of digital technology, leading to the digitalization of contemporary society. This circumstance seeks to emphasize how people ascribe significance to the kid's developmental processes, specifically questioning "what constitutes the framework that digitalizes the child, the family, or society?" This study seeks to provide a foundation for future research and applications by elucidating the impact of digitalization on the everyday life processes of children within a theoretical framework.

Conversely, these theoretical frameworks will enhance our comprehension of the article's primary subject and allow us to approach it from a larger viewpoint. This research examines the following primary questions and hypotheses:

2.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

Question 1: How does digitalization in the context of the family affect children in the modern world?

Hypothesis 1: It affects the weakening of ties with external reality, taking the family as a role model, neglecting the family, decreasing communication skills and becoming isolated.

Question 2: How does the digitalization of society affect today's children? (Taking their favorite cartoon character/artist as a model, difficulty distinguishing between fiction and reality, behavioral changes, consumption)

Hypothesis 2: Changes in today's society show that childhood is being abstracted from traditional childhood culture and transformed into a digitalized childhood.

Question 3: How do the traces left by digital platforms affect children's developmental processes?

Hypothesis 3: Eating disorders (obesity, excessive weight gain/loss), psychological disorders (depression, anxiety disorder), academic problems (inability to focus on a task for a long time), physical disorders (back pain, headache, tingling in the hands and arms), etc. affect.

2.3. Research Method

This article provides a literature analysis and study undertaken to investigate the impact of the digitalization of children on the perceptions of families and society. The literature review used sources from scientific publications, academic papers, and pertinent theses.

2.4 Data Collection Techniques and Analysis Process in the Research

was examined on the " DergiPark AKADEMIK" platform. The advanced search portion of the webpage was accessed first. In this literature review, the term "Child" was chosen for the title section, while "Digital," "Media," "Culture," and "Family" were picked as keywords. Subsequent to the selection, the items on the resultant page were organized chronologically by year. The scanning criteria established by the researchers were assembled by collecting publications published between August 2002 and November 2023, which were granted access permissions. The

abstract and methodology portions of the papers found during the scanning process were examined to ascertain the relevance of the study's topic to digitalization. Following the brief evaluation, it was determined that 31 papers were under the study's scope. In the summary evaluation, it was determined that five papers were appropriate for the study objective. A total of 36 items were obtained, and the scanning procedure was concluded. This systematic review delineates the research rationale, the study's objectives, and the results section. The papers used in the research were converted to PDF format on the computer, and the acquired data were analyzed.

3. FINDINGS

A sequence of circumstances in a child's childhood may significantly contribute to the development of digital addiction. The primary issue is the inability to form interpersonal interactions. Altun et al., 2022. ³Lack of communication within the family, or the lack of communication between parents and their children, who spend time with their mobile phones to relieve the tiredness of the day when they come home in the evening, will create a feeling of loneliness and introversion in the child.

When examining how digitalization affects children in the modern world in the context of the family; As a requirement of modern life, people establish new bonds with the help of communication channels that can be used via the internet, and although this situation may seem positive, it causes traditional family ties to weaken and ⁴turn into a nuclear family structure and individuals to become lonely (Akbaş and Dursun, 2020). Digitalization, which begins with the

³Altun , D. and Erden, F. (2022). Digital Technology Applications, Research and Trends in Early Childhood. Ankara: Nobel Publishing. p. 28

⁴ Akbaş, Ö. Z., & Dursun, C. (2020). The impact of technology on the family: Digital parents and children of the changing family. *Turkish Studies-Social* , 15 (4), p. 2248.

change in communication methods within the family, also affects social changes, causing communication skills to decrease and individuals to become lonely. A child who becomes lonely within the family and strengthens the "culture of not leaving his room" will also negatively affect communication between individuals.

Today, factors such as economic conditions, widespread urbanization, diversification of family structure, increased participation of women in the workforce, individualization of family members with the new social structure formed in urban areas have affected parent-child relationships and caused changes in the attitude and expectations of society towards children (Merdin, 2017, p.39).⁵ Contemporary living conditions compel parents to ensure their children access various opportunities essential for modern society, such as sports, foreign language education, musical talent, and art, while also adapting to technological advancements and promoting women's involvement in the workforce, thereby influencing family dynamics. The mother's neglect of her child due to prolonged working hours, particularly during the crucial language development phase of 0-3 years (infancy), coupled with her self-sacrifice to compensate for the child's emotional growth, will adversely impact both the child and familial communication. This circumstance will indirectly hinder the child's social adaptation if he/she lacks essential attention and affection. The absence of communication among parents within the family will indirectly undermine the child's connections to external world.

Through the social learning paradigm, children replicate the behaviors shown by their parents. The influence of other adults, including parents, in both social and virtual environments affects children's development (Yıldırım, S. 2019, p. 110).⁶ In contemporary family dynamics, the first action upon leaving house is to consult the cell phone (nomophobia), and the absence of this device becomes the day intolerable. Absence prior to entering the virtual environment indicates that the experience of deprivation in reality demonstrates the world has undergone various transformations. This circumstance influences children's conduct due to digitization and is seen as an integral aspect of existence.

In an era when the physical world is accessible via mobile devices, the influence of digitalization shapes children's purchasing patterns and behavioral modifications. The incidence of youngsters developing internet addiction is growing daily. Internet addiction is typically characterized by an

⁵ Merdin, E. (2023). The place of children in the lives of different generations. *Early Childhood Education Researches*, 1 (1), p. 39

⁶ Yildirim, S. (2019). Media and Child Abuse . *Anasay Publications*. 10 (3) p.110

inability to resist excessive internet use, a diminished perception of time spent offline, heightened irritability and aggression when deprived of internet access, and a progressive decline in an individual's professional, social, and familial life (Arisoy, 2009).⁷ In circumstances where a child experiences deprivation, such as lacking internet access in social settings, having a depleted battery on their phone or tablet, or lacking a compatible charger, manifestations may include crying episodes, irritability, aggression, diminished self-control, feelings of insecurity, and uncertainty about how to proceed, all of which can adversely affect the child's cognitive awareness. The digital era has transformed children's conventional play cultures and toy preferences via the integration of all aspects into consumption. Today's toys dominate several households, thereby leading to behavioral issues in youngsters. The children's want for more toys, shown via tantrums, anger, and tears when denied their desired item, underscores the significance of consumerism and marketing. Today, the global toy market has attained a valuation of 80 billion dollars. The gaming and toy industry in Turkey is valued at 700 million dollars. The representation of childhood and the image of children cannot be dissociated from the marketing tactics of global corporations. (Sormaz, F. & Yüksel, H. 2012, p. 986).⁸ Consequently, it is evident that contemporary children have become a focus in toy consumption. During the pre-operational stage (ages 2-7), children have not yet acquired logical reasoning abilities, making their perception of item imagery a significant aspect of consumer culture.

A critical component in the target audience being children is their inability to discern right from wrong at this developmental stage, as their capacity to differentiate truth from fiction is not yet completely matured. Advertising businesses have primarily targeted families to purchase goods and services associated with cartoon or animation characters, including toys, stationery, personal items, textiles, furniture for children's rooms, and food products, as shown in television ads. İnal observes that, as seen in our everyday experiences, the introduction of a cartoon is often followed

⁷Arisoy, Ö. (2009). Internet Addiction and Treatment. *Current Approaches in Psychiatry*. 1 (1), p. 56

⁸ Sormaz, F. and Yüksel, H. (2012). Changing childhood, industrialization of games and toys and consumer culture. *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*. 11(3), p. 986

by an influx of merchandise featuring its characters. The cultural industry of imperialist nations, such as the USA, generates virtual heroes like X-Man, Spider-Man, Pokémon, and Terminator, alongside a global neoliberal 'childhood culture' in assertive manifestations. This phenomenon aligns with the exigencies of the wars waged by the USA to achieve global dominance” (Sormaz, F. and Yüksel, H. 2012, p.1000)⁹ Young children do not process visual and auditory stimuli in the same manner as adults and are influenced differently. Children struggle to differentiate between fantasy and reality. (Ergüney, M. 2017, p. 1923).¹⁰ This scenario may lead individuals to display actions that might be detrimental to their well-being. Instances of this phenomenon sometimes appear in the news, such as youngsters impersonating Pikachu or Spiderman and leaping from windows.¹¹ In contemporary society, children adopt cartoon characters or social media influencers as role models, replicate their lifestyles, seek analogous products for personal use, attempt to align their fashion choices, become engrossed in their own imaginative realms through repetitive viewing of scenes, and struggle to differentiate between reality and the virtual world. The current societal condition prevents youngsters from fully enjoying their lives; the products they acquire fail to sustain their happiness over time and adversely impact their developmental domains, resulting in irreparable psychological and physiological consequences.

Candy is included in the lists of digital gaming addictions. Games such as Crash, Minecraft, and Roblox - Adopt Me may adversely affect a child's physical development, nutrition, and psychological well-being. Digital gaming addiction may result in physical consequences like postural disorders, obesity, and hand numbness, as well as psychological impacts such as irritability, abrupt mood fluctuations, and a disconnection between the virtual and real worlds.¹² In this context, if a situation adversely impacts children's daily lives, it manifests through behaviors such as losing in games (exhibiting irritability, throwing tantrums, biting, or hitting). Additionally, when a child who has spent hours in front of a screen transitions to a different environment, they may experience anxiety, insecurity upon leaving their room, and depressive symptoms. When

⁹ Sormaz, F. and Yüksel, H. (2012). Changing Childhood, Industrialization of Games and Toys and Consumption Culture. *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*. 11 (3), p.1000

¹⁰Ergüney, M. (2017). A Study on the Effects of the Internet on Preschool Children. *Ulak bilge Journal*, 5 (17), p.1923

¹¹ (Http://www.hurhaber.com, Access Date: 24.10.2017; alkislarlayasiyorum.com Access Date: 24.10.2017) can be seen.

¹² Şimşek, E and Yılmaz, TK (2020) “Systematic Review of Methods and Results in Digital Game Addiction Studies Conducted in Turkey”. *Kastamonu Education Journal* 28 (4), p. 1853.

parents impose a time restriction on their kid, seeing behaviors such as loneliness and nail-biting correlates with an increase in screen time within their daily routine, thereby impacting sleep patterns and contributing to different sleep disorders.

The child's mental development is adversely impacted by excessive computer and internet use. The child's development is hindered when interactions with family and friends are supplanted by electronic relationships, adversely impacting interpersonal communication and communication abilities. Consequently, one might assert that a direct correlation exists between poor internet use and sadness, asocial behavior, and loneliness. Ergüney, M. (2017). p. 1920.¹³ In contemporary society, the substitution of real-life friendships with computer or tablet games, which foster a digital existence, will impact interpersonal connection in social contexts. Joining a new social circle can pose challenges in initiating and sustaining communication skills, particularly when attempting to convey information through inverted sentences, and when the interpretations of expressions differ from those of the interlocutor, which adversely impacts face-to-face interactions.

Internet addiction engenders several more issues. Internet addiction also induces bodily issues. The primary issues are ocular abnormalities, adverse effects of radiation, and musculoskeletal alignment difficulties. Ergüney, M. (2017). p. 1922 Following the digital era, children's dependency on technology gadgets significantly influences their screen time. Particularly during the period of confinement resulting from the COVID-19 epidemic, children's bedtimes have also altered. Children that struggle with sleep onset have reduced sleep duration, attributed to altered melatonin levels resulting from prolonged exposure to blue light. Recent observations indicate that youngsters exposed to prolonged bright light are increasingly using corrective eyewear and experiencing optic nerve inflammation, impaired vision, dry eyes, myopia, and difficulties with ocular adaptation.

¹³Ergüney, M. (2017). A Study on the Effects of the Internet on Preschool Children. *Ulak bilge Journal*, 5 (17), 1920-1922 .

The new generation is rapid. The rise in food-style nutrition intake has led to prolonged screen time, leading in health issues such as obesity and cardiovascular risk. The rise in desk time is concurrently elevating the need of physical therapy. Prolonged computer usage, due to the strain on muscle groups from repetitive motions, leads to conditions such as 'carpal tunnel syndrome', characterized by discomfort, numbness, and weakness in the hands (Ergüney, M. 2017, p.1922).¹⁴ Factors such as an inability to rise from one's location in everyday life, a sedentary lifestyle, and a reduction in physical activity will adversely impact physical well-being. Moreover, computer and internet use significantly contribute to the limitations in physical activity, decline in personal cleanliness, incidence of headaches, irregularities in physical development, and weight gain in children and teenagers. Currently, children who spend excessive time in front of screens, have restricted physical environments (such as streets, neighborhoods, or public squares), or lack opportunity to engage in physical activities away from screens, are likely to have health issues related to insufficient physical activity. Children are progressively disengaging from many activities, including swimming, cycling, climbing, and leaping. This circumstance is seen to influence the physical aspects of children's sedentary lifestyle.

The duration of screen exposure for youngsters adversely impacts their educational pursuits and cognitive development processes. Excessive use of digital media tools diminishes children's cognitive abilities, isolates them from social interactions, and passively inhibits the right hemisphere of the brain, which governs practical thinking, creative pursuits, creativity, and social skills.¹⁵ Screen addiction not only undermines a child's social connections but also induces mental exhaustion, since the mind is always engaged and unable to relax. The inability of a child who frequently uses the internet to regulate computer usage (planning skills), coupled with a lack of engagement in artistic pursuits such as music, ceramics, and sports, as well as social alienation and detachment from artistic activities, diminishes cognitive capacity.

The preference of school-age children for the virtual world over real-life social interactions, such as school trips and family outings, may impact the relationship between sensory stimulation and social engagement. Moreover, although these instruments provide youngsters the chance to see the world from their vantage point, they inadequately stimulate other senses, primarily engaging just sight and hearing. For instance, youngsters may recognize the sight and name of a local dish on

¹⁴ Ergüney, M. (2017). A Study on the Effects of the Internet on Preschool Children. *Ulak bilge Journal*, 5 (17), p. 1922 .

¹⁵Yilmaz, D and Guney, R. (2021). *The Effects of Media on Children and Recommendations on Its Use*. *Dokuz Eylul University Faculty of Nursing Journal*. 14 (4), 486-487.

television, although they cannot comprehend its flavor. ¹⁶ Consequently, it is underscored that direct experiences significantly influence the ability to perform efficiently in everyday life. The family's value assessments influence the connection with the kid and impact the child's linguistic development. In the digital era, it has become prevalent for parents seeking personal time to play cartoons during their infant's mealtime to occupy themselves with their phones, to play children's songs in crowded settings to prevent their baby from crying and disturbing others, and to hand their phone to their baby while traveling to soothe a fussy child. This condition will also impact the foundations of language development, a crucial aspect of a child's future existence.

Hutton et al. (2020) observed that prolonged digital screen usage in children aged 3-5 delays the development of white matter in the brain that underpins language and literacy skills, resulting in these youngsters exhibiting poor item naming and reading abilities. Children who devote extensive time to screens, concentrating only on one medium, are influenced by rapid and fluid imagery, which may hinder their ability to alter existing cognitive schemas.

Prolonged television viewing (2-3 hours per day) throughout early infancy may contribute to the development of ADHD (11). Early stimulation of brain processes significantly influences cognitive development throughout infancy. In this instance, premature activation of cerebral processes would hinder the establishment of functional neural connections, impair the child's perceptual system, and adversely affect attention continuity. The remnants of the two-dimensional virtual environment, which habituate the child's cognitive processes and attention spans to lethargy, will subsequently influence the child's academic life.

During this time when attention regulation is essential, television captivates the child's focus with many rapidly displayed moving pictures, hindering the child's growth (12). Prolonged screen usage for a youngster may impair their capacity to follow instructions in everyday activities. For instance, when parents request something from the child: (After you put your dark-colored clothes in the washer, can you feed the fish?) The child modifies the material by either adding or subtracting

elements not specified by the parent, entirely neglecting the requested expression and failing to recall the instructions upon approaching the parent with inquiries such as, "What should I do?" Furthermore, as the duration of screen time increases, cognitive skill deficits may emerge, complicating the retrieval of fragmented information at irregular intervals. When children commence primary school, parental support in navigating digital technology is crucial for managing screen time and understanding real-life responsibilities, essential for their development as healthy individuals.

3.1 Data on Children's Use of Social Media

In recent years, it can be seen that the duration youngsters spend in front of screens has altered alongside their lifestyle patterns. It has been shown that 35.9% of children aged 6 to 15 read less books due to increased screen use. This was followed by 33.5% engaging in reduced study, 27.7% allocating less time to family, 25.4% interacting face-to-face with friends and playing less games, and 17.2% experiencing diminished sleep. (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2021). Consequently, children's perceptions of the circumstances resulting from their screen time and associated metrics were elucidated using numerical data. The decline in internet use rates has hindered their educational growth and familial interactions. This has altered the routines that youngsters assign to their everyday activities.

Table 1. Distributions of Situations Caused by the Time Children Spend in Front of the Screen

Çocukların düşünceleri (%)	6-15 Yaş			6-10 Yaş			11-15 Yaş		
	Toplam	Erkek	Kadın	Toplam	Erkek	Kadın	Toplam	Erkek	Kadın
Daha az ders çalışıyorum	33.5	36.3	30.5	31.4	33.1	29.6	35.6	39.5	31.5
Ailemle daha az vakit geçiriyorum	27.7	30.3	24.9	24.8	27.0	22.4	30.6	33.6	27.5
Daha az kitap okuyorum	35.9	39.3	32.2	32.9	34.7	30.9	38.9	43.9	33.6
Daha az uyuyorum	17.2	18.0	16.4	14.9	14.7	15.1	19.5	21.3	17.6
Arkadaşlarımla yüz yüze daha az görüşüp daha az oyun oynuyorum	25.4	27.1	23.5	23.5	24.1	23.0	27.3	30.3	24.1

Source: TurkStat, 2021a. (The table is in Turkish, the explanations are in the text.)

A critical concern highlighted in the chart is that youngsters do not get enough sleep. While youngsters need to be reading books prior to sleep, they diminish their quality of life by prolonged exposure to blue light. This scenario necessitates that parents contemplate diligently and implement appropriate safeguards. (Altun et al., 2022). In this context, enhancing early literacy experiences in early childhood and primary education, along with the strategic implementation of

selected programs, will augment the child's interactive book reading engagement with the family and positively influence the child's reading habits.

3.2 Data on Children's Use of Digital Technology Ownership

As to TÜİK 2021 statistics, 32.3% of youngsters aged 6-15 who use mobile phones/smartphones routinely check their devices at least every 30 minutes, with 32.8% for males and 31.7% for girls. No gender disparity exists, and comparable outcomes are seen.

43.5% of children aged 11-15 routinely use a cell phone or smartphone and report checking it every half hour, whilst 16.5% of children aged 6-10 do the same. Analyzing these figures suggests that youngsters are likely to exhibit a rise in digital addiction imminently. The prevalence of children who consistently utilize a mobile phone or smartphone, checking it at least every 30 minutes, checking it last before sleep and first upon waking, and using it while watching television or dining with others is 3.7%, whereas the proportion of children engaging in at least one of these behaviors has significantly risen to 52.4%. This scenario serves as a hallmark of rapid digitization in contemporary society.

Table 2. Phone Usage Behaviors of Children Who Use Mobile Phones/Smartphones Regularly, According to Age Group

Source: TÜİK, 2021b (The table is in Turkish, the explanations are in the text.)

has emerged as a significant study subject globally and in Turkey during the COVID-19 pandemic. This research investigates how perceptions of digitalization are formed from infancy in contemporary society and examines the influence of family and community members on different developmental outcomes in children.

3.3 Conceptual Background on the Digitalization of Children in a World That Has Lost Its Reality

The pace of technological advancement is evolving daily. Children born into the digital age are entering a virtual realm shaped by technological systems that influence attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions, including robotic coding, nanotechnology, the metaverse, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR), extending beyond traditional internet, mobile devices, computers, and tablets. As digital technology grows pervasive in our society, it is transforming into a framework that influences the lives and everyday routines of both parents and people. The research on the current issue has been analyzed, and a summary of the key studies is shown in the table below.

Table 3. Analysis of Children Growing Up in the Digital World from Different Perspectives

RESEARCHER	RESEARCH TITLE	RESEARCH SUBJECT	FINDINGS
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<p>Karaboga, MT 2018</p>	<p>Children and Children's Culture in the Media Age: Reflections of Violence and Consumer Culture</p>	<p>This study aims to examine the purposes in which media institutions differ from social institutions such as schools and families, the developmental consequences of children's consumption of media content (advertisements, TV series, cartoons, etc.), and the changes in media program content in children.</p>	<p>Ministry of Family, Social Policies and Health</p> <p>A platform where the Ministry will be present and joint work will be carried out</p> <p>It is needed that the media should be able to improve children's book reading habits.</p> <p>causing the loss of culture, children being packed in front of the screen</p> <p>It has been concluded that spending long periods of time with images and dreams distances them from their own dreams and dulls them, and that the impact of violence and consumer culture is great.</p>
<p>South, Z. 2020</p>			<p>As a result of the findings, it was concluded that while</p>

	A Study on Children's Social Media Use.	The study investigated how 5th grade students' social media usage levels, sharing frequencies, and the child's age, preferences, and environmental factors changed.	the age of using technological devices with the internet was decreasing, the usage rates were decreasing. It was determined that the reason for using social media was being influenced by family and friends.
Gencer, TE and Aktan, MC	Changing needs and problems in the digital age and society: the	As the age we live in experiences an uncontrollable	As a result of this study, it is necessary to include current

	<p>Children Entrusted to Digital Media and Screens</p>	<p>To identify possible risks and dangers that children and young people may encounter in virtual environments in today's digital media use;</p> <p>Parent and educator interactions regarding access to these environments were examined in the research.</p>	<p>in the home environment have expanded, and the use of technology has become holistic in the family, revealing the necessity for parents to be good literate.</p>
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4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research investigates the impact of a child's desire for embodiment in a virtual environment on contemporary family and societal structures amidst rising global dangers. The repercussions of the COVID-19 epidemic on people have heightened the significance of digitization via the transition to a digital education system. The primary objective of the research is to investigate, from a broader viewpoint, the degree to which the digitalization of children impacts the lives of parents and persons within society.

The study's findings indicate that the connection formed with digital technology is more influential than that with the mother, altering the dynamics of family structure in contemporary lives. This scenario underscores the significance of digital media use, the child's interaction with their primary familial relationships, and the impact of media on the child's development.

In contemporary society, the use of digital media technologies has escalated, reflecting the diversification of children's everyday activities. As children's screen time grows, their reading of books and family interactions have diminished, altering their behaviors and patterns. This assertion is substantiated by the quantitative data from TÜİK's 2021 study on children's information technology use. An analysis of the phone use patterns of youngsters who frequently utilize mobile devices indicates that their tendency to check their phones at least every 30 minutes underscores the prevalence of digital addiction. The absence of communication within the family, along with the influence of children on their parents' conduct and perception of role models, impacts children's personality characteristics and actions. This circumstance seeks to marginalize those who embrace the inescapable cycle of reality and are not engaged in the virtual realm.

This research examines the evolving family lifestyle and societal responsibilities in the digital era from many viewpoints that constitute its foundational framework. A collaborative platform is essential for the Ministry of Family and Social Policies and the Ministry of Health to address digital life skills, emphasizing the significance of understanding the impact of digital literacy on a child's development within the family context.

The research currently indicates The suggestions emphasize the necessity of incorporating contemporary concepts pertinent to the digital age into the educational curriculum, equipping children with the skills to regulate screen time, manage personal information associated with digital device usage, understand the real-world ramifications of digital environments and respond appropriately, as well as develop planning skills for digital media utilization. Furthermore, it is asserted that rather than observing children becoming engrossed in technological devices and the

digital realm, there is a necessity for more extensive research to examine parental engagement in digital book reading activities from a more profound and holistic viewpoint, as well as to assist digital platforms in refining their strategies accordingly. Future research should concentrate on extensive studies that explore digital literacy education from early childhood, rather than addressing issues such as virtual loneliness, cyberbullying, violence in digital games, and digital media addiction affecting children in their media usage.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The research is limited to the compilation of internationally and nationally published books, articles and scientific papers on the subject.

NOTIFICATION

Financial Support: No financial resources were used for this study.

Conflict of Interest: There are no conflicts of interest among the authors contributing to this study.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

The publication ethics of Ankara Education and Research Social Sciences Journal; It is a national-based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for

the findings and creations of others and works to realize this in the field of social sciences, aiming for these principles. Helsinki Declaration criteria have been taken into consideration.

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